

FOSTERING INNOVATION THROUGH KNOWLEDGE SHARING: EXPLORING BARRIERS, ENABLERS, AND POLICY INTERVENTIONS IN EMERGING MARKETS

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Abstract. *This article aims to identify and analyse the barriers as well as enablers to effective knowledge sharing within organizations and their impact on innovation performance. Identifying obstacles and also, exploring the key enablers of best internal practises that promote knowledge sharing and foster innovation.*

The study will contribute to the Knowledge-Based View (KBV) by providing empirical insights into the mechanisms of knowledge sharing and its impact on innovation. It will also extend the Absorptive Capacity and SECI models by exploring its applicability in different organizational contexts. There will be discussion about that KBV can be enriched by integrating Absorptive Capacity and SECI, as both are processes through which organisations manage and exploit knowledge to foster innovation (Grant,1996).

After Identifying the enablers as well as barriers to inter-organizational knowledge sharing, this research aims for developing knowledge sharing strategies which are specifically tailored for SMEs to overcome these barriers. The findings will provide actionable recommendations for managers and leaders on how to foster a culture of knowledge sharing and overcome barriers to innovation. This will be particularly valuable for SMEs in their early stages of growth and seeking to enhance their innovative capabilities. Also, the finding may help policymakers design programs to strengthen SME innovation ecosystems.

This article discusses academic research articles, reports, and relevant books written by the experts of Innovation and Knowledge management. It concludes with Results, discussion and recommendation part.

Keywords: *innovations, Knowledge Sharing, Absorptive Capacity, SCIE Model, Open Innovation.*

Introduction

The Virtuous Cycle of Knowledge Exchange and Innovation. The notion that a combination of internal idea generation and external knowledge absorption can cultivate a fertile environment for innovation to thrive is a compelling concept that deserves further exploration. Organizations that proactively participate in the dissemination of their own knowledge not only enrich the broader knowledge landscape, but also strategically position themselves to reap the reciprocal rewards of this sharing (Huang & Rice, 2009).

The value of knowledge sharing lies in its ability to facilitate the dissemination, implementation, and development of existing knowledge (Fauziyah & Rahayunus, 2021). As employees engage in the exchange of their knowledge, experiences, and skills, they are stimulated to think more creatively, effectively, and innovatively (Fauziyah & Rahayunus, 2021).

Breakthrough Innovations is the result of extensive Knowledge sharing in Organisations; KS does not only benefit the organisations but also it fosters the Individual creativity and

innovativeness across the teams by challenging the existing assumptions, perspectives and diverse ideas (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). KS can help to uncover hidden potential as it requires from people to refine and articulate their ideas prior to sharing, leading to deeper insights and connections (Sveiby, 2001). Furthermore, knowledge sharing helps build a culture of collaboration and openness which are considered as key components for sustaining long-term innovation efforts (Zahra & George, 2002). When the organisations create an environment where free exchange of ideas are enabled, this can encourage the collective intelligence of the workforce and outside partners, fostering innovative. This can be done by enabling the employees to interact freely physically and virtually. Also, encouraging experimentation and autonomy are in the top of the list of enablers of KS. Interestingly, as one of the important aspects of achieving a competitive advantage, innovation is also dependent on knowledge sharing enablers, such as top management knowledge value and reward systems have been identified as the main pillars (Iqbal, 2021), among an organization's employees (Delio I.Castenade and Sergio Cueller, 2020).

Methodology

The methodology for this literature review article involves a comprehensive review of existing research on the intersection of knowledge sharing (KS) and innovation. This approach ensures a thorough and unbiased synthesis of the current state of knowledge, identifying key themes, gaps, and future research directions. To ensure a thorough review, multiple academic databases and sources were consulted, including: Google Scholar, JSTOR, Web of Science and Scopus. A combination of keywords and search terms related to KS and innovation were used. These include: “Knowledge Sharing”, “Innovation”, “KM practices”, “Absorptive Capacity”, “Open Innovation”, “SCIE Model”.

Literature Review

Innovation Enabler: Knowledge sharing among employees

Knowledge sharing (KS) among employees is considered as the main driver of innovation and the source of competitive advantage, and it is also critical point where creation and application of knowledge in organization happens. According to Storey and Kelly (2002), lack of knowledge is considered as the main barrier to Innovation. As KS encourages Innovation, it is almost impossible to be Innovative without KS (D. Castaneda and S.Cuellar, 2019). According to Nonaka (1996) organizations should create an environment where culture supports knowledge sharing, innovation, and collaboration.

Authors Marie Josee Roy et.al., (2024) surveyed 3,652 respondents who were employed by government agencies and collected their responses regarding effective KS channels. According to their research authors found that 50% of the respondents mentioned traditional way of KS as the most effective method among employees, such as colleague feedback, team meetings and informal exchange. These are direct communication tools and especially important for new hires to build interpersonal relationships and integrate with company’s culture. Another method to KS was mentioned as digital KS channels, such as intranets, extranets, search engines, document repositories and e-learning platforms. Respondents confirmed that availability of both traditional and digital channels of KS enhanced their competency development, especially during onboarding process.

Halmstadtr (2003) defined knowledge sharing as interactions between human actors where raw material is knowledge. In this instance, it is appropriate to mention that knowledge is divided into two categories: Tacit and Explicit. Tacit knowledge is deeply rooted in personal experience

and is often challenging to express or transfer, such as instinctive problem-solving or craftsmanship skills (Polanyi, 1966). Explicit knowledge, however, is structured, documented, and easily shared, such as written instructions or formal reports (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). Combining these two forms of knowledge enables organizations to leverage individual insights while ensuring broader accessibility and application. This interplay is foundational for innovation, as described in frameworks like the SECI model, which outlines processes for transforming tacit knowledge into explicit formats for organizational benefit (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995).

Additionally, by definition Knowledge sharing is the exchange of experience, skills, and tacit and explicit knowledge among employees, in the context of organizations. Competitive advantage is achieved to higher levels when employees in organization are communicated openly about changes. Employees are seen as critical source of resilience in organization as well as their abilities to adopt, recover and proactively develop both themselves and workplace resources (Young Kim, 2021). When there is two-way and open communication environments and employers provide timely, accurate, unequivocal and balanced information to their subordinates, it will turn the organization to more resilient and innovative one (Sharma and Sharma, 2019). Interestingly, while KM is instrumental in enhancing innovation, the relationship is not one-dimensional. For instance, in the context of library management services, fostering a culture that encourages staff to share ideas can lead to innovative outputs, demonstrating the reciprocal nature of KM and innovation (Rambeli & Yunus, 2018).

1.2 Knowledge sharing is not an automatic process: In the competition-intensive business environment, innovative work behaviour (IWB) of its employees is the main source of competitive advantage over competitors for organizations to rely on (Mohamed Haffar et. el., 2021). As a result of their research, Mohamed Haffar et. el (2021) argue that although Knowledge sharing is among the top strategic actions within the organisation, it does not mean that process is automatic all the time. Therefore, authors researched preconditions that would enable innovation-related activities in the SMEs. According to Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) KS is the main source of Innovation and survival of the organization. KS is also important for improving organizational creative thinking abilities and innovative behavior among employees (Rahman et.al 2016; Dong et.al 2017). Radaelli et.al (2014) argued that in the process of completing work-related activities, KS enables employees to exchange valuable expertise and information and it is essential for firm's success. The authors also mentioned that the creativity and novelty of the ideas by employees are highly dependent on the strength of KM policies in the organization. The role of human resource management in applying KM practices further illustrates the multifaceted approach required to foster innovation within enterprises (Karasek, 2018). Accordingly, the contribution of KM to promoting innovation is also significant in small businesses, where sharing knowledge processes are essential for innovation in product, marketing, and organizational domains (Harel et al., 2020).

The literature shows the importance of KM in driving innovation across various sectors and organizational contexts. Effective KM practices, such as creating an environment conducive to knowledge sharing and creativity, are integral to the innovation process and competitive advantage. These practices not only facilitate the generation of new ideas but also ensure that these ideas are effectively implemented, leading to enhanced innovation performance within organizations (Kumari & Singh, 2022; Patwary et al., 2022).

Studies have also shown that organizations with strong KM policies, which encourage information sharing and employee retention, are more likely to engage in innovative activities (Kremp & Mairesse, 2004). Moreover, the creativity of manufacturing firms has been linked to both codified and uncoded KM practices, suggesting that the way knowledge is managed can influence the extent of innovation (Landry & Amara, 2001).

Innovation Enabler: Co-creation and Crowdsourcing

2.1 Co-Creation with Employees. Even though R&D is an important factor in innovation process, major part of innovations is not created in R&D but within the process of knowledge sharing among skilled workforce, interactions with outside or other firms and public research institutions, and encouragement in the firm for learning and exploiting knowledge among its people. Due to the fact that finding information can be costly even in the cases of information being open, having effective channels of information, communication and skills transmission within the organisation in the process of diffusion of knowledge is highly important (OSLO manual, 2005).

Open innovation strategies heavily rely on knowledge sharing to support inbound innovations which is acquiring external knowledge through partnerships, collaboration and observations of trends in industry or outbound knowledge sharing is about disseminating research findings or collaborating in some projects during innovation processes (Enkel, E., Gassmann, O., & Chesbrough, H., 2009). Research indicates that network collaborations act as enablers of knowledge flows between organizations, improving their ability to innovate. These networks foster both the absorption of diverse external knowledge and the dissemination of internal expertise, which collectively drive innovation performance and competitiveness (Crupi, A., et.al., 2020; Laursen, K., 2006).

Inter-organizational Knowledge management has been found to be crucial for strategic knowledge sharing among allied organizations, which in turn supports innovation (Tsai, 2016). Including Employees from different levels in decision-making, known as Open Innovation strategy, gives them opportunities to take part and use their operational knowledge when innovating. However, the research undertaken by Violetta Splitter and colleagues (2024) showed that although catching the attention of top management initially, the inability of lower-level employees to convey information frustrated and distracted the CEOs who were first excited about the idea of including mid-and-lower level of management. After several attempts to convert and convey information differently, mid-lower-level management employees developed competence in delivering meaningful, engaging and compelling messages. Particularly, it worked well when employees shared their novel ideas to corporate themes (Strategic Management Society, May 2024). Competence of employees in combining local knowledge with corporate themes developed during the strategy making process, they learned it through experiential learning of hands-on experience while crafting the strategy (Mintzberg, 1987; Kolb, 1984) and through their observations (Bandura, 1971; Splitter, Seidl and Whittington, 2024).

Researchers Zyngo et. al 2018, looked at Open innovation from three perspectives. The first perspective was Problem-solving where innovation problems of the firm placed at the centre of attention. Second approach was Change in established organisation where open innovation is supported as new mode of management. It consists of three phases such as: unfreezing, moving and institutionalising. And, finally the last one was the micro foundations perspective. Large body of research confirms, that if an organisation wants to implement a new management capability, it

needs to develop the micro foundations which include three categories: individuals, processes and structures.

Following are the Micro foundations that can enhance Open innovations in firms.

Number one is Individuals as gatekeepers, according to researchers Andreos Zyngo et.al (2018), it is crucial to have individuals who acts as a bridge between organisation and external partners. They play an important role in flow of information from external sources and integration of that new knowledge in company's innovation processes.

In terms of process, having well defined processes are crucial to innovate in general, when it comes to Open innovation, in such cases firms should pay even more attention in crafting their processes well.

After having well defined processes, organisations then can invest more time in their structures in coordinating their activities in alignment with organisational learning.

2.2 Co-Creation with Outside Stakeholders of Firm. Innovative performance of firms can be enhanced through Knowledge sharing and support for creativity by leadership of the organisation (Cabrilo & Grubic-Nesic, 2013; Kyriazopoulos & Samanta, 2009). These authors also mentioned that when fostering the innovation, technology enhanced innovations in KM can play an important role.

Open innovation has emerged as a powerful approach to enhance innovation performance in organizations (Zynga et al., 2018). Traditionally, firms have relied on internal research and development to drive innovation. However, the open innovation paradigm emphasizes the importance of engaging with external partners to access and leverage knowledge beyond the firm's boundaries (Bigliardi et al., 2020) (Yun et al., 2018). One example of successful open innovation in the context of knowledge sharing is the collaboration between companies founded by James Watt and Steve Jobs (Yun et al., 2018). These entrepreneurs recognized the value of collaborating with different partners to develop and commercialize new business ideas, which allowed them to discover new forms of value creation for their target customers (Yun et al., 2018). Similarly, in the food industry, companies that are not capable of using external knowledge often resort to partnerships with technology providers, suppliers, and competitors to access the necessary and drive innovation (Bigliardi et al., 2020).

In this intensely competitive environment, an organization alone cannot innovate in isolation; they need to collaborate and engage with wide range of partners, including suppliers, customers, universities, research centres or even competitors (Bigliardi and Galati, 2013). It is in the purpose of acquiring resources and ideas from external environment. From this paradigm, it is necessary for organisations to loosen their boundaries rather than tightening, it is because in Open innovation knowledge inflows and outflows are intentional, and the system of relationships includes external partners to a wide range (Billiard, B. et.al , 2020).

According to Chesbrough and Brunswicker (2014) the most challenging part of Open innovation for firms is changing process from closed to open innovation regime. Another research by Lutgens et. al (2014), aligned with this finding that after implementing Open innovation into their practises, firms then might find it challenging to make it permanent in their toolboxes.

Barriers to Innovation: Policy and regulations

Innovation systems approach, when formulating Innovation policy and having a clear idea of how innovation process works, it is most appropriate to have a better understanding of barriers and drivers of innovation that can impact the innovation process properly. Although measurement

of innovation in the enterprise is the most difficult one to obtain, it is also the most important one to have.

Several factors hamper the Innovation activities, slows down the process, or may even be the reason for not starting the Innovation process at all. These may include factors such as costs that are too high or lack of demand by customers, firm-level obstacles such as not qualified or skilled workforce, and legal factors such as taxes or regulations. It is also recognized now that in order to sustain any development in the economy, the role of several actors, such as governments, civil society, entrepreneurs, universities, and private sector, do play an important role (ideainnovation.org, 2024). Here it is relevant to illustrate some information about E.M. Roger's theory on Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) from 1962, which is considered as one of the earliest social science theories. According to this theory, the target audience accepts and starts to use the new product, behavior or idea once it has reached the final stage of diffusion or spread. The targeted groups for diffusion can be varied and depend on the context of the innovation (CPRL Report, 2017).

Innovation Barrier: Disconnection between Academia and Production sector

Inputs of Innovation include R&D, Financial resources, and human inputs such as ideas, leadership, and attitudes, including human creativity with self-efficacy. If there is a lack of investment in new knowledge generation, it results with market failures (D. Moraes Silva, 2023). Also, indivisibility and problems in its appropriability, increased risk and uncertainty result with the innovation activity becoming costly. These factors add to the emergence of market, financial and demand barriers to innovation, where the intervention of government will be required to solve the obstacles.

The speed and quality of knowledge created in HEIs, can contribute to creation of knowledge-based economies enormously (Iqbal, 2021). Knowledge-based view of the organization defines knowledge as the most valuable strategic asset of the firm. This framework suggests that the competitive advantage and superior performance of an organization over its competitors comes from its ability to generate, transfer, acquire, and exploit the knowledge in a better form than others. Here it is appropriate to give basic comparison between Knowledge Based View and Resource Based View: When considering two perspectives on competitive advantage, the Ricardian and Schumpeterian views, it is important to note that they complement each other rather than contradict. The Ricardian perspective suggests that economies should focus on producing goods and services in which they excel. On the other hand, the Schumpeterian perspective emphasizes the importance of innovation, creative destruction, and radical changes in production methods rather than incremental improvements. These two approaches work together to achieve success in a competitive marketplace. (Pereira & Bamel, 2021). Research undertaken by Quyen, T., et. al., (2024) mentioned that relationship between academic and productive sectors is not strong in transition countries and as a result, they show weak innovation systems. It is specifically because of the transition process and perceived traditions of firms which effects to the level of demand for knowledge by the productive sector. By being a highly complex process, changing from centrally planned economy into market economy, there was a change in both micro and macro level in developing country's economy. During the process along with destroying the old resources and values, perceived old matrix of the firm also needs to be changed.

Theoretical Framework

5.1 Absorptive capacity Theory of Cohen and Levinthal (1990)

Absorptive capacity, as defined by Cohen and Levinthal (1990), is an organization's ability to recognize the value of new external knowledge, assimilate it, and apply it for commercial purposes. This concept emphasizes the role of learning and knowledge management in innovation and organizational growth.

AC is a crucial dynamic capability in KM and Innovation processes in SMEs, it can enable firms to have access to Complementary Knowledge which can complement their own. This complementary knowledge can be fuel to drive Innovation performance. In a dynamic market as such now, ability to absorb and apply this knowledge contributes to Innovation performance. (Benhayom,L, et.el, 2021).

Cohen and Levinthal (1990) emphasizes the importance of absorptive capacity as critical factor in organisational learning and innovation. As a result of their research, author developed framework (Diagram 1) that shows the process of acquiring, assimilating, transforming and exploiting knowledge. Absorptive capacity of the firm is very important factor in firm's innovativeness, because it determines the ability of how well the firm is able to leverage the external knowledge, such as technological developments, adaptation to market changes and being innovative to create competitive advantage over other competitors (Cohen, 1990).

According to Cohen and Levinthal (1990) absorptive capacity components, namely acquisition, assimilation, transformation and exploitation are interrelated. To exploit the new knowledge, the firms must have the ability to acquire, assimilate and transform it first. In this instance, it is important to mention that firm's prior knowledge in the field plays a crucial role when to recognise, interpret and apply new knowledge into their processes. Also, it was confirmed through authors' research that firm's who constantly built up their knowledge in particular domain, kept advancing and innovating in that area constantly. The framework results showed that firms should not only concentrate in internal R&D research but also try to absorb and integrate external knowledge to keep up with dynamic market changes and to gain competitive advantage.

The dimensions of absorptive capacity (AC) are typically categorized into two main components: Potential Absorptive Capacity (PACAP) and Realized Absorptive Capacity (RACAP). Each of these components consists of specific dimensions: First component is Potential Absorptive Capacity (PACAP) that includes Acquisition and Assimilation Dimensions. The Second Component is Realized Absorptive Capacity (RACAP) which includes Transformation and Exploration stages (Alvaro C. and Rui H., 2017).

Diagram 1: Absorptive Capacity Framework: (Source: Adapted from Alvaro C. and Rui H., 2017)

5.2 SECI Theory of Nanoka and Hirotaka (1996)

In their famous research in Knowledge sharing, Nonaka and Hirotaka Takeuchi (1996) created SECI model which shows the four modes of knowledge conversion in organizations. The first one is Socialisation also called tacit to tacit where people share knowledge directly by telling each other best practices and tactics, observing others in action, and imitating or practicing together. Second method is Externalisation (tacit to explicit), in this model tacit knowledge is documented through reflection, dialogue, or conceptualisation. This can take the form of models, hypothesis, metaphors or analogies. The third way is the Combination (explicit to explicit) here knowledge is synthesized and combined into more advanced sets of explicit knowledge. Through sorting, adding, combining and categorising existing explicit knowledge. Last model, fourth one is Internalisation (Explicit to Tacit) according to authors this model is about the fact that knowledge is internalized by individuals by absorption. Facilitating SECI environment demands from leader of higher level of abilities to be the role model and sharing the vision with employees well. It is also important for organisation to learn and adapt to changes, used new knowledge to improve products, processes and services. It requires investments in trainings, developments and KM practices

Diagram 2: The SECI Model (Source: Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1996)

Research Gap

Existing research on the impact of knowledge sharing on SME innovation outcomes is limited, with methodologies primarily focused on larger firms. While the role of Absorptive Capacity (AC) and SCIE models are well-documented in large enterprises, there is insufficient exploration of how SMEs, especially in less-developed countries, build and utilize the combination of AC and SCIE. The dynamics of inbound and outbound knowledge sharing within internal and external networks remain underexplored in these contexts. This study addresses the gap by examining best practices for fostering effective knowledge sharing in resource-constrained SMEs to drive innovation.

Discussions and Recommendation for fostering Innovation through KS

Day G. (2024) argues that there are three linked processes to innovation that growth leaders use, and when used systematically these can bring success to the firm. The following are the processes: first one is to look for potential opportunities, the second one is to evaluate market prospects and how they align with their future aspirations, and lastly, select the most appropriate concepts to go with. However, in practise most of the leaders use reactive approach to innovation where they match or leapfrog their innovations by copying or adapting to competitors' innovations.

Building Strategic Alignment, the key to balancing absorptive capacity and knowledge sharing is strategic alignment. Creating mechanisms that protect vital knowledge while fostering

knowledge often requires individuals to articulate and refine their ideas, which can lead to deeper insights and unexpected connections, further fuelling the innovation process.

Collaboration and co-creation, fostering collaboration is a powerful strategy to drive innovation within organizations and across industries. By bringing together diverse perspectives, skills, and knowledge, collaborative efforts can spark creativity and lead to breakthrough ideas. This approach encourages the cross-pollination of concepts from different domains, often resulting in novel solutions to complex problems. Effective collaboration also promotes a culture of open communication and shared responsibility, which can accelerate the innovation process and improve the quality of outcomes.

Innovation systems approach, In Oslo manual (2005), there is a key element of innovation policies that directed to help overcoming the potential obstacles that innovative firms might face in developing countries. Third edition of Oslo manual also incorporated innovation systems approach in a new chapter on linkages in the innovation processes. Well-being of the nations, development and economic growth required generation, exploitation and diffusion of knowledge in any given country. According to this believe both policy discussions and innovation research confirms that innovations should be looked from broader perspectives.

Knowledge-intensive production is widely used in most developed economies and it has resulted with improvement in high-technology manufacturing and business services.

Innovation systems approach supports the role of government in regulating, monitoring and creating conditions that encourages innovative initiatives by firms as conditions, regulations and policies have vital role in innovativeness of firms. Also, this approach leads the idea of institutional creation, diffusion and application of knowledge as widely as possible within the organisation. Innovation systems approach, according to Smith (2000), is process where innovation carried out by firms is complex interaction between a firm and environment not purely independent decision making.

In conclusion, to maximize the benefits of collaboration for innovation, organizations can implement various strategies. These may include creating dedicated spaces for interdisciplinary teamwork, establishing cross-functional project teams, and leveraging digital platforms to facilitate remote collaboration. Additionally, fostering a supportive environment that values experimentation and tolerates failure as part of the learning process is crucial. By incentivizing collaborative behaviour and recognizing team achievements, organizations can cultivate a mindset that views innovation as a collective endeavour rather than an individual pursuit, ultimately leading to more robust and impactful innovations.

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